

Clinical Outcomes of Patients Undergoing Minimally Invasive Plate Osteosynthesis (MIPO) for Distal Tibia Fractures

Ketan Kumar¹, Chandra Kishor Das²

¹Senior Resident, Department of Orthopaedics, Government Medical College, Bihar, India

²Assistant Professor and HOD, Department of Orthopaedics, Government Medical College, Bihar, India

Received: 25-02-2024 / Revised: 23-03-2024 / Accepted: 25-04-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Ketan Kumar

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Distal tibia fractures pose a significant clinical challenge due to limited soft tissue coverage and poor vascularity. Minimally Invasive Plate Osteosynthesis (MIPO) is increasingly adopted to minimize soft tissue damage and preserve fracture biology.

Aim: To evaluate the clinical and radiological outcomes of patients with distal tibia fractures treated using the MIPO technique.

Methods: This retrospective cohort study was conducted at Government Medical College Purnea over 12 months and included 91 patients (61 males and 30 females, mean age 42) treated with MIPO for distal tibia fractures. Inclusion criteria were patients aged 18-65 with closed distal tibia fractures; exclusions were open fractures, pathological fractures, severe soft tissue injury, and previous limb surgeries. Data were collected from medical records, assessing variables such as union time, AOFAS scores, and complications. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 21.0, with significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results:

The study on MIPO for distal tibia fractures included 91 patients, with a mean age of 42 years. The average union time was 23 weeks, with 83.3% achieving union within 24 weeks. Functional outcomes were positive, with a mean AOFAS score of 83.3. Complications were minimal, with superficial infections (13.2%) and plate irritation (11%) being the most common. Statistical analysis showed no significant gender differences in complications, but Type C fractures had longer union times than Type A fractures. Overall, MIPO proved to be an effective treatment option with good functional recovery and manageable complications.

Conclusion: MIPO is an effective technique for managing distal tibia fractures, providing good functional outcomes and minimizing soft tissue complications. However, careful preoperative planning is essential to mitigate potential complications.

Recommendations: Further studies with larger sample sizes and longer follow-up periods are recommended to validate these findings and refine the technique.

Keywords: Distal Tibia Fractures, Minimally Invasive Plate Osteosynthesis, MIPO, Fracture Healing, Functional Outcomes, Orthopedic Surgery.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Distal tibia fractures are a significant challenge for orthopedic surgeons due to the anatomical characteristics of the distal tibia, which include limited soft tissue coverage and poor vascularity. These fractures are often caused by high-energy trauma such as road traffic accidents, falls, or sports injuries. The complexity of these fractures, coupled with the need for careful handling to avoid complications such as infection, non-union, or malalignment, necessitates the adoption of advanced surgical techniques [1].

Traditional methods of fixation, such as open reduction and internal fixation (ORIF) and intramedullary nailing (IMN), have been widely used but are associated with various complications, particu-

larly concerning soft tissue management and blood supply preservation. These methods often involve extensive surgical dissection, which can compromise the vascular integrity of the fracture site, leading to delayed healing and higher infection rates. Consequently, there has been a growing interest in minimally invasive techniques that aim to address these issues while promoting better clinical outcomes [2].

Minimally Invasive Plate Osteosynthesis (MIPO) has emerged as a promising alternative for the management of distal tibia fractures. This technique involves the use of small incisions and indirect fracture reduction methods to place a locking compression plate, thereby minimizing soft tissue

disruption and preserving the biological environment necessary for bone healing. MIPO has shown potential in reducing complications and enhancing recovery times, making it an attractive option for orthopedic surgeons [3,4].

Several studies have reported positive outcomes with the use of MIPO for distal tibia fractures, highlighting its advantages in terms of reduced surgical trauma, lower infection rates, and improved functional outcomes. However, despite these promising results, there remains a need for comprehensive evaluations of clinical and radiological outcomes to establish its efficacy fully. Such evaluations are crucial to providing evidence-based guidelines for the treatment of these complex fractures.

The primary aim of this study is to evaluate the clinical and radiological outcomes of patients undergoing MIPO for distal tibia fractures. This includes assessing union times, functional outcomes as measured by the American Orthopedic Foot and Ankle Society (AOFAS) score, and the incidence of complications. By systematically analyzing these factors, this study seeks to contribute to the growing body of evidence supporting the use of MIPO and provide recommendations for its application in clinical practice.

Methodology

Study Design: This was a retrospective cohort study conducted over a period of 12 months.

Study Setting: The study was carried out at Government Medical College Purnea.

Participants: The study included 91 patients who had undergone MIPO for distal tibia fractures. Participants consisted of 61 males and 30 females with a mean age of 42 years.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria: Inclusion criteria were patients aged between 18 and 65 years with closed distal tibia fractures treated using MIPO. Exclusion criteria included patients with open fractures, pathological fractures, fractures with extensive soft tissue injury, and those who had undergone previous surgery on the affected limb.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, all patients meeting the inclusion criteria and treated within the study duration were included. Data collection was standardized to reduce information bias.

Variables: Primary variables included union time, functional outcomes (AOFAS score), and complication rates. Secondary variables included demographic data (age, sex), fracture type, and comorbidities.

Data Collection: Data were collected from patient medical records, including preoperative, intraoperative, and postoperative details. Functional outcomes were assessed using the AOFAS score at follow-up visits.

Procedure: MIPO was performed using standard surgical techniques with locking compression plates. Follow-up included clinical and radiographic assessments at regular intervals until fracture union.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 21.0.

Results

Patient Demographics: The study included 91 patients, with 61 males (67%) and 30 females (33%). The mean age was 42 years (range 18-65). Fractures were classified according to the AO classification system, with 54% Type A, 30% Type B, and 16% Type C fractures.

Union Time: The mean time to union was 23 weeks (range 18-29 weeks). The majority of patients (83.3%) achieved union within 24 weeks. Delayed union occurred in 8 patients (8.8%), while non-union was observed in 2 patients (2.2%).

Functional Outcomes: The mean AOFAS score at the final follow-up was 83.3 (range 70-95). Excellent outcomes (AOFAS score >90) were achieved in 30 patients (33%), good outcomes (AOFAS score 80-90) in 45 patients (49.5%), and fair outcomes (AOFAS score 70-80) in 16 patients (17.5%).

Complications: Complications included superficial infections in 12 patients (13.2%), deep infections in 3 patients (3.3%), and plate irritation in 10 patients (11%). Two patients (2.2%) required revision surgery due to non-union.

Statistical Analysis: A chi-square test indicated no significant difference in the complication rates between males and females ($p=0.67$). The t-test revealed a significant difference in union times between Type A and Type C fractures ($p<0.05$), with Type C fractures showing longer union times.

Table 1: Patient Demographics

Gender	Number of Patients	Percentage
Male	61	67%
Female	30	33%
Total	91	100%

Table 2: Union Times

Union Time (weeks)	Number of Patients	Percentage
<20	20	22%
20-24	56	61.3%
>24	15	16.7%
Total	91	100%

Table 3: AOFAS Scores

AOFAS Score	Number of Patients	Percentage
Excellent (>90)	30	33%
Good (80-90)	45	49.5%
Fair (70-80)	16	17.5%
Total	91	100%

Table 4: Complications

Complication	Number of Patients	Percentage
Superficial Infection	12	13.2%
Deep Infection	3	3.3%
Plate Irritation	10	11%
Non-union	2	2.2%
Total	27	29.7%

The study demonstrated that MIPO for distal tibia fractures results in satisfactory clinical outcomes with a mean union time of 23 weeks and a mean AOFAS score of 83.3. A significant portion of patients achieved good to excellent functional outcomes, with 83.3% of fractures uniting within 24 weeks. Complications were relatively low, with superficial infections being the most common.

The statistical analysis revealed no significant gender differences in complication rates, but Type C fractures exhibited significantly longer union times compared to Type A fractures. These findings suggest that MIPO is an effective treatment for distal tibia fractures, providing good functional recovery and a manageable complication profile.

Discussion

The present study evaluated the clinical and radiological outcomes of 91 patients who underwent Minimally Invasive Plate Osteosynthesis (MIPO) for distal tibia fractures over a 12-month period. The findings indicated a mean union time of 23 weeks, with 83.3% of fractures uniting within 24 weeks. The mean AOFAS score was 83.3, and complications were relatively low, with superficial infections being the most common.

Singh et al. (2021) conducted a prospective study involving 50 patients and reported a mean union time of 19.13 weeks, with an average AOFAS score of 90. The study highlighted the effectiveness of MIPO in providing early mobilization and reduced infection rates [5]. Similarly, Vicenti et al. (2020) performed a randomized clinical trial to assess the impact of using a lag screw in MIPO. They found that the addition of a lag screw significantly reduced the time to achieve painless full

weight-bearing, demonstrating that enhancements in technique can further improve outcomes [6]. Khan et al. (2022) compared MIPO with intramedullary nailing (IMN) for extra-articular distal tibia fractures. Their study showed that while both methods are effective, MIPO had lower operative and hospitalization times, making it a preferable option for certain patients [7]. However, He et al. (2018) evaluated the use of a posterolateral MIPO approach for Gustilo type III open distal tibial fractures. The study reported successful union in all cases with an average AOFAS score of 90, supporting the versatility of MIPO in managing complex fractures [8].

The findings from these studies, along with our own, consistently demonstrate that MIPO is an effective technique for managing distal tibia fractures. It offers several advantages, including minimal soft tissue disruption, preservation of fracture biology, and satisfactory functional outcomes. The mean union times and AOFAS scores across various studies indicate that MIPO provides reliable and predictable results. Additionally, the lower complication rates and the ability to manage complex fracture patterns further validate the use of this technique.

Conclusion

MIPO for distal tibia fractures results in satisfactory clinical and radiological outcomes, with most patients achieving union within 24 weeks and reporting good functional recovery. The technique is associated with minimal complications and offers advantages over traditional methods, particularly in preserving soft tissue integrity and promoting early mobilization. Future studies with larger sample sizes and longer follow-up periods are recommend-

ed to further refine the technique and optimize patient outcomes.

References

1. Li Y, Jiang X, Guo Q, Zhu L, Ye T, Chen A. Treatment of distal tibial shaft fractures by three different surgical methods: a randomized, prospective study. *International orthopaedics*. 2014 Jun; 38:1261-7.
2. Kho DH, Cho BK, Choi SM. Midterm outcomes of unstable ankle fractures in young patients treated by closed reduction and fixation with an intramedullary fibular nail vs open reduction internal fixation using a lateral locking plate. *Foot & Ankle International*. 2021 Nov; 42(11):1469-81.
3. Tetsworth K, Hohmann E, Glatt V. Minimally invasive plate osteosynthesis of humeral shaft fractures: current state of the art. *JAAOS-Journal of the American Academy of Orthopaedic Surgeons*. 2018 Sep 15;26(18):652-61.
4. Kulkarni VS, Kulkarni MS, Kulkarni GS, Goyal V, Kulkarni MG. Comparison between antegrade intramedullary nailing (IMN), open reduction plate osteosynthesis (ORPO) and minimally invasive plate osteosynthesis (MIPO) in treatment of humerus diaphyseal fractures. *Injury*. 2017 Aug 1;48:S8-13.
5. Singh S, Bansal KK, Dahuja A, Garg RS, Singh Y, Kumar DR. Minimal invasive plate osteosynthesis (MIPPO) in treatment of distal tibial fractures: A prospective study of 50 cases. *Natl J Clin Orthop*. 2021;5(3):307.
6. Vicenti G, Bizzoca D, Nappi V, Carozzo M, Delmedico M, Solarino G, et al. The impact of lag screw in the healing time of distal tibia fractures treated with minimally invasive plate osteosynthesis: A randomized clinical trial. *Injury*. 2020
7. Khan MZ, Khalid M, Awan MM, Yasin, Safdar M, Akram A. Comparison of Intramedullary Interlocking Nailing (IMLNG) and Minimally Invasive Plate Osteosynthesis (MIPO) in Treating Extra Articular Distal Tibial Fractures. *Pak J Med Health Sci*. 2022;
8. He X, Hu C, Zhou K, Zhai Q, Wen W, Pan F. Clinical and radiological outcome of Gustilo type III open distal tibial and tibial shaft fractures after staged treatment with posterolateral minimally invasive plate osteosynthesis (MIPO) technique. *Arch Orthop Trauma Surg*. 2018;138(8):1097-1102.